

Significant Linguistic Information on the Arabic and Hausa Languages

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Abstract

This paper investigates significant linguistic information on Arabic and Hausa languages. Linguistic information on any natural language of the world belongs to the fields of historical linguistics or diachronic linguistics (which studies the development of language and languages over time as well as their historical development) and philology (the study of language history). The significant information on these languages as provided by the researcher in this study includes how their names came to be, their locations and ethnographies, their genetic and typological classifications as well as their sociolinguistic profiles and dialectal issues. As a matter of fact, the typological and diachronic or philological linguistic information of this kind is highly necessary for linguists or scholars, students, language enthusiasts and laymen as it brings to their fingertips in a single study or article such information that is basic for any kind of study in the languages under focus in this paper as well as other languages of the world. This article has also brought to the front burner the acclaimed genetic relationship between these two Afro Asiatic languages, hence making this study a worthy exercise.

Introduction

Providing or supplying the significant or fundamental linguistic information about a language at any level of linguistic study such as phonology, morphology, syntax, pragmatics or sociolinguistics, is of extreme importance, and it should be a usual practice or norm for language scholars. Apparently, the reason for this remains sacrosanct: languages did not just fall from the sky. They actually belong to specific branches of the trees of family of languages typologically. And besides, such linguistic information provides a window through which languages are viewed by the linguist. In other words, by such information, the linguist is equipped with vital firsthand information about such languages. In fact, it is like tracing the route of something, which takes one to the destination of that thing, and thereby leading one to know that which is needed about that thing at last, whether good or evil, as the case may be.

ARABIC: Name, Location, Demography and Ethnography

The name *Arabic* is derived from the word *Arab*, which is said to have originated from a Syriac pun by Abraham. According to this account, Abraham addresses Ishmael and calls him *u'rub*, from Syriac *'rob*, meaning mingle. One other account says the name originates from Al Hirah (fourth-to-seventh-century Mesopotamia) in the north, while yet another says it originates from the south of Arabia, from Himyar (110 BC to AD 525). According to Webb (2016:35-6), history reports its first apparent *Arab* or *Arabic* in annals of the Iraqi-based Neo-Assyrian Empire (911-612 BCE).

The Assyrians pushed their frontiers towards south-western deserts where they encountered nomadic camel-herding peoples whom their administrators labelled with names such as *Arba-a*, *Aribi*, *Urbi* etc. These names sound to us like *Arabic*, and thus purportedly depict the earliest generations of ‘the Arab people’. Whatever it is, the fact remains that Arabic is one of the ancient and major languages of the world. Arabic is the only surviving member of the Ancient North Arabian dialect group attested in pre-Islamic Arabic inscriptions dating back to the 4th century. Arabic is written with the Arabic alphabet, which is an abjad script and is written from right to left.

Demographically, Barakat (1993:27) reports that the Arab homeland extends from the Gulf and the Zagros mountains on the Iranian frontier in the east to the Atlantic Ocean in the west, and from the Taurus range on the Turkish border in the north to Central Africa beyond the Sahara and the Horn of Africa in the south. The Arab world stretches 5.25 million square miles, which is composed of twenty-three states, inhabited by a mostly young population with over 400 million inhabitants. Arab population encompasses a vast geographical region that extends from Iraq in the east to Morocco in the west. They occupy the whole of Mesopotamia, Middle East, Arabian Gulf, North Africa, as well as some parts of East and West Africa. Arab populations are distributed in these 23 different countries, namely: Algeria, Bahrain, Comoros, Djibouti, Egypt, Eritrea, Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Mauritania, Morocco, Oman, Palestine, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Somalia, Sudan, Syria, Tunisia, United Arab Emirates, and Yemen. Arabs do not just homogeneously populate this geographical area; they also tend to concentrate highly in narrow locations such as the Nile, Euphrates, and Tigris valleys, the coastal regions of North Africa, the Gulf, and Western Asia. As commented by Harb (2016:4), the aforementioned twenty-three countries are designated as the League of Arab States by the United Nations (UN). In addition, Mirkin (2010:9), the population of the Arab countries nearly tripled between 1970 and 2010, climbing from 128 million to about 400 million. According to the medium variant projection, the Arab Region will have 598 million inhabitants by 2050. Furthermore, the population of the Arab world is similar in size to that of the U.S. or of the European Union. The Arab world is diverse, with people from different ethnic, religious, and cultural backgrounds. Skin colour ranges from white to black, with sometimes wide variations seen within the same country. Barakat (1993:4) further declares that the current “modern” borders of Arab countries were artificially decreed by the infamous Sykes-Picot Agreement of 1916, through which the French and British colonial

powers divided the region into their respective spheres of influence. While direct colonization of some Arab countries ended with the end of the Second World War, some countries did not gain their independence until 1971 (e.g. Bahrain, Qatar, UAE). The region continues to be of significant geostrategic importance as nearly half of the world's total proven oil reserves are in Arab countries, making the region "the world's single most important supplier of crude oil". Similarly, Mirkin (2010:7) states that the Arab Region, which lies at the crossroads of Europe, Africa and Asia, is the cradle of civilization and the birthplace of the three great monotheistic religions of the world. The Region benefits from a number of similarities and opportunities, including a long, rich history spanning thousands of years, strong cultural traditions, common language and a large, educated workforce, due in part to increasing female labour force participation. The Region also sits atop more than half of the world's oil resources.

Ethnographically, as revealed by Barakat (1993:62-3), Arab cities are often described as a mosaic of neighbourhoods based mainly on their religious, ethnic, and socio-economic composition. This characteristic is slowly being undermined, but many cities continue to exhibit aspects of it. Cairo, for instance, preserves some of the old divisions in separate quarters and subquarters based on ethnic and socioeconomic groupings. While each quarter increasingly shares many common features with the rest of the city, some of its identifying marks have survived modernization and economic reorganization. Furthermore, the link between neighborhoods and important ethnic, sectarian, and social class divisions was clearly visible in the city of Beirut during and prior to the then civil war. Some quarters and suburbs of Beirut were predominantly inhabited (and quite often named for) Sunnis, Shi'ites, Orthodox Christians, Maronites, Druze, Armenians, Kurds, and other groups. Similar linkages characterize most other eastern Arab cities, such as Damascus, Baghdad, Aleppo, Jerusalem, and Amman. Lastly, it is not out of place to say that the most distinctive features of Arab social organization include tribal solidarity based on blood and symbiotic ties, and what the anthropologist, Lancaster (1981) calls "premises of equality, autonomy and the acquisition of reputation".

Historically, developments across the 23 countries have shaped four main cultural divisions within the Arab world, as stated by Harb (2016:5); namely: the Fertile Crescent (a crescent-shaped region capping the Arabian Desert/Arabian Peninsula), the Nile Valley (located in eastern North Africa), the Gulf states (situated in the Arabian Peninsula), and the Maghreb (situated in western North Africa). These are expatiated below:

One, **the Fertile Crescent**: This area includes Palestine, Jordan, Syria, Lebanon, and Iraq. The territory is historically rich, being the birthplace of two of the world's monotheistic religions (Judaism and Christianity), and the location of some of the oldest continuously inhabited cities in the world. People living in this part of the Arab region are especially diverse in ethnicities and religious sects, a diversity that is both a blessing (bringing e.g. cultural wealth) and a curse (bringing e.g. sectarian and ethnic tensions). The Fertile Crescent has been plagued by decades of conflict and wars, with the Israeli–Arab conflict (ongoing since 1948), and the U.S. invasion of Iraq in 2003 as two infamous examples. The region continues to be marred by internal and sectarian conflicts (Iraq, Lebanon, Syria), and it is also a stage for proxy wars.

Two, **the Nile Valley**: This region contains what was once the largest country in Africa, i.e., Sudan, before its southern section split into a separate nation in 2011, and the most populous nation in the Arab world, Egypt. Egypt is distinguished by its millennia-old history, mixing both its Ancient Egyptian Pharaonic past and Arab-Islamic identity. Egypt's rich history and demographic weight give it a pivotal role in inter-Arab politics and relations, and a central role in the Israeli–Arab conflict. Egyptian politics has been dominated by rivalries between nationalist-secular and Islamic parties (e.g. the Muslim Brotherhood), and all Egyptian presidents from Egypt's independence to the uprisings of 2011 came from military backgrounds.

Three, **the Gulf States**: This region includes the Kingdoms of Saudi Arabia and Bahrain, as well as Kuwait, Qatar, and the UAE. The arid Arabian Peninsula, home to Islam's holiest site, Mecca, saw little development until the discovery of oil over a century ago and the socio-economic boom that followed. The monarchies of the Gulf have allowed few political freedoms, and have relied instead on strong family networks and ties, and a strict enforcement of perceived religious norms to enforce their rule. Some cities in the Gulf, such as Dubai (UAE) and Doha (Qatar), have witnessed massive and rapid economic development and physical expansion, and have become globalized international destinations.

Four, **the Maghreb**: Nations in this region include Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Libya, and Mauritania, who have currently formed an economic development union, called "Union du Maghreb Arab". The large Sahara Desert and the Atlas mountain range favoured the Maghreb's relations and trade with Mediterranean countries, especially with France, a former colonial power (French language is widely used in Morocco, Tunisia, and Algeria). Conflict over the Western Sahara area, as well as conflict over the civic and cultural rights of the 30-million-strong Amazigh

people, continues to sour inter-Maghreb relations. As in many Arab countries, the power struggle between nationalist/secular parties and religious ones is decades old, and varies from bloody conflict (e.g. the Algerian civil war of 1991-2002) to relatively peaceful political transitions (e.g. the Tunisian uprising of 2011).

Lastly, Ajami (2016:120) observes that Arabic culture is abstract-oriented. By this, he means that the identity of the Arabs resides in Arabic language because languages are abstract, and that whatever we speak and write are just representations of language. Therefore, the identity of the Arabs is abstract, as most of the Arabs are Muslims, but some are Christians. Hence, religion doesn't determine the identity of the Arabs. In addition, Arabs have different skin colours and origins. Therefore, skin colour and origin do not define an Arab. All of this shows that the only factor which determines who is an Arab is in Arabic language itself, such that an Arab gains his or her identity as being an Arab by virtue of the fact that he or she speaks Arabic.

Genetic and Typological Categorization

As proclaimed Al-Huri (2015:28), Arabic is a member of Semitic languages which include a number of languages in the Middle East and North Africa. It is originally generated from Afro-Asiatic languages which includes besides Arabic different languages such as Hebrew, Ethiopian and others. The first emergence of Arabic as a world language goes back to the seventh century CE. In a similar fashion, Bishop (1998:1), while tracing the root of the Arabic language, observes that it descends from a language known in the literature as Proto-Semitic. This relationship places Arabic firmly in the Afro-Asiatic group of world languages. Furthermore, Bishop (1998:1) says that Ruhlen's (1987) taxonomy in his *Guide to the World's Languages* helps to elucidate Arabic's ancestry within this large group of languages. Specifically, Arabic is part of the Semitic subgroup of Afro-Asiatic languages. Going further into the relationship between Arabic and the other Semitic languages, Modern Arabic is considered to be part of the Arabo-Canaanite sub-branch of the central group of the Western Semitic languages. Thus, while Arabic is not the oldest of the Semitic languages, its roots are clearly founded in a Semitic predecessor. The common ancestor for all Semitic languages (i.e. Hebrew or Amharic) in the Afro-Asiatic group of languages is called Proto-Semitic. Based upon reconstruction efforts, linguists have determined many of the phonological, morphological, and syntactic features of Proto-Semitic. As might be expected, not all Semitic languages have preserved the features of their common ancestor language. In this

respect, Arabic is unique, in that it has preserved a large majority of the original Proto-Semitic features.

As an Afro-Asiatic family of languages which consists of over three hundred languages, Arabic and Hebrew are two unique examples of the living languages. In the early times, Arabic was found as an inscription in the Syrian Desert dating back to the fourth century. During this period, Arab tribes, who lived in the Arabian Peninsula and neighbouring regions, had a thriving oral poetic tradition. Ryding (2005) as cited in Al-Huri (2015:29) indicates that because of the paucity of the written records, little is known about the nature of Arabic of those times, between the third and seventh centuries, adding that the only written evidence is in the form of epigraphic material (brief rock inscription and graffiti) found in the Northwest and Central Arabia. Abu-Absi (1986) as cited in Al-Huri (2015:29) reports that the Arabic writing system is an adoption of Syriac and Nabataean scripts, both of which were derived from Aramaic; although this script was known to the Arabs in Pre-Islamic times, it acquired its sanctified status only after it was put into the service of Islam.

There are two basic divisions of the Arabic language. They are: Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) and Colloquial Arabic. The Modern Standard Arabic originates from the Classical language of the Quran, and in the view of almost all Arabs, it is the “correct” Arabic. It is worthy of note to say that the Modern Standard Arabic emerged as a result of Arabs’ contact with the Western culture and the dire need of assimilating the new political, technological and technical terms that had not been included in the Arabic dictionary. It is the most widely used in education, mass media, religious sermons and official speeches, it is practically no one’s mother tongue, and good proficiency in it requires more than elementary education. On the other hand, Arabs use the colloquial language in all their daily interactions, meaning it is the language which is spoken regularly, and which Arabic speakers learn as their L1. It is painlessly and naturally acquired with no need of schooling or learning grammar as it is the case with MSA. However, when they encounter a language situation calling for greater formality, Modern Standard Arabic is the medium of choice. So, in every area of the world where Arabic is spoken, this language situation prevails (Bishop, 1998 and Al-Huri, 2015). Below is a family tree of Proto-Semitic languages clearly showing the position of Arabic:

Figure 1: The Genetic and Typological Classification of Arabic in the Proto-Semitic Language Family (<https://www.thenational.ae/arts-culture/examining-the-origins-of-arabic-interactive-1.184175>)

Sociolinguistic Sketch and Dialect Information

While sociolinguistics is the study of the relationship between language and society, a dialect is a distinct form of a language, possibly associated with a recognisable regional, social, or ethnic group differentiated from other forms of the language by specific linguistic features (e.g. pronunciation, or vocabulary, or grammar, or any combination of these). They also note that no human language is fixed, uniform, or unvarying; all languages show internal variation. Actual usage varies from group to group, and speaker to speaker, in terms of the pronunciation of a language, the choice of words and the meaning of those words, and even the use of syntactic constructions (Akmajian et al., 1995:259).

In the light of this, Al-Huri (2015:32) says that there is consensus among linguists of the reality of Arabic varieties, have emerged as a result of the cultural and linguistic contact between the nomadic tribes of Arabian Peninsula speaking Arabic on one hand, and people of the conquered regions during the expansion of the Islamic empire who had spoken different languages on the other, besides the various processes of development to which Arabic has been undergone over the years. Versteegh (1997) as cited in Al-Huri (2015:32) reveals that “important changes occurred in the Arabic language as a consequence of its spread over an enormous territory and its contact with many different languages such as south Arabian, Persian, Greek, Berber, etc. Zaidan and Callison-Burch (2012:3) give a breakdown of Arabic dialects and groups them into five categories, as outlined below:

- (i) **Egyptian**: the most widely understood dialect, due to a thriving Egyptian television and movie industry, and Egypt’s highly influential role in the region for much of 20th century;
- (ii) **Levantine**: a set of dialects that differ somewhat in pronunciation and intonation, but are largely equivalent in written form; closely related to Aramaic;
- (iii) **Gulf**: folk wisdom holds that Gulf is the closest of the regional dialect to MSA, perhaps because the current form of MSA evolved from an Arabic variety originating in the Gulf region. While there are major differences between Gulf and MSA, Gulf has notably preserved more of MSA’s verb conjugation than other varieties have;
- (iv) **Iraqi**: sometimes considered to be one of the Gulf dialects, though it has distinctive features of its own in terms of prepositions, verb conjugation, and pronunciation; and
- (v) **Maghrebi**: heavily influenced by the French and Berber languages. The Western-most varieties could be unintelligible by speakers from other regions in the Middle East, especially in spoken form. The Maghreb is a large region with more variation than is seen in other regions such as the Levant and the Gulf, and could be subdivided further.

To sum it up, Zaidan and Callison-Burch (2012:3) observe that there is a reasonable level of mutual intelligibility across the dialects, but the extent to which a particular individual is able to understand other dialects depends heavily on that person’s own dialect and their exposure to Arab culture and literature from outside of their own country. For example, the typical Arabic speaker has little trouble understanding the Egyptian dialect, because of Egypt’s history in movie-making and television show production, and their popularity across the Arab world. On the other hand, the Moroccan dialect, especially in its spoken form, is quite difficult to understand by a Levantine

speaker. Therefore, from a scientific point of view, the dialects can be considered separate languages in their own right, much like North Germanic languages, e.g. Norwegian, Swedish, Danish, and West Slavic languages, e.g. Czech, Slovak, Polish, etc. Arabic is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world, and the General Assembly of the United Nations (UN) adopted it as one of its 6th official languages alongside Chinese, Russian, English, French and Spanish in 1974 (Al-Huri, 2015:28).

HAUSA: Name, Location, Demography and Ethnography

Ochonu (2008) as cited in Unubi and Yusuf (2017:415) reports that the name *Hausa* (also known as Hausawa and Kasar Hausa) denotes the language, people, and land of the Hausa respectively, which are actually fairly recent coinages. The modern usage probably originates from the writings of Othman bin Fodio, leader of the Fulani Jihad, who before and during the Jihad, homogenized the Hausa-speaking but autonomous peoples. Hausa is not just a language; it is a category that has become synonymous, and now correlates, rightly or wrongly, with certain ways of acting, expressing oneself, making a living, and worshipping God. Hausa now carries with it a constellation of cultural, economic, and political connotations. As a language of trade and social contact in West Africa, and as the language of an ethnic group known as Hausa, it has now assumed a cosmopolitan position. The presence throughout much of West Africa of people who speak Hausa as a second language, and the role of the Hausa language as a lingua franca in much of northern Nigeria, speaks to the utilitarian importance of a language whose intertwinement with trade and itinerant Islamic practices dates back to a remote Nigerian antiquity. Unubi and Yusuf (2017:415) quote Kraft and Kirk-Green (1994) as saying that Hausa is primarily the name of a language rather than of a people. By extension, it has come to be used to describe the majority group of northern Nigerians and south-central Nigeriens, linked by a sense of unity based on a common language, history and customs. The present-day Hausa people originate from the Hausa Bakwai, the seven historical states of Kano, Katsina, Daura, Zazzau (Zaria), Biram, Gobir and Rano, which form the nucleus of the Kano, North Central and North-western states of Nigeria and of the contiguous portion of Niger Republic.

Demographically, Lamb (date?) as also cited in Unubi and Yusuf (2017:415) says that Hausa land forms part of the belt of Savannah which stretches across from the Atlantic to the Red Sea. This belt lies between the desert in the North and the coastal equatorial forests to the South. Generically, it is named the Sudan, from the Arabic Beled as-Sudan - Blackman's Land. The gently

undulating countryside is only sparsely forested and the higher areas without mountains remain as uncultivated bush. According to Wolff (date?), Hausa language is an important lingua franca in West and Central Africa, and it is spoken as a first or second language with the population of over 40 million people. Their primary religion is Islam and considered to be the 4th largest Moslem bloc in the world with a reasonable number of known Christians, and a sizeable number of follows of African traditional religion. The Hausa people are the largest ethnic groups in West Africa and the largest ethnic group in Africa. They are chiefly located in the Sahelian areas of Northern Nigeria and south-eastern Niger, with significant numbers also living in parts of Cameroon, Ghana, Côte d'Ivoire and Sudan. Predominantly, Hausa communities are scattered throughout West Africa and on the traditional Hajj route across the Sahara Desert, especially around the town of Agadez.

Geographically, Hausa land is significantly situated at the joining point of different ethnic groups – the Southern indigenous people and the Hamitic strain from North Africa. Rainfall occurs between June and September, leaving the mainly farming population with ample time to develop crafts and, until comparatively recent times, to conduct war. In the rainy season, farming demands the full attention of the whole family. Travelling at this time used to be especially difficult, whereas in the dry season the rivers dried up and communication became easy. Until comparatively recent times the roads were poor, so donkeys and camels were widely used.

Historically, the cherished legend of Hausa origins is based on the marriage of Bagdad Prince Abuyazida to the Queen of Daura after slaying a giant snake which occupied the town's only well and terrorized the townspeople. The seven children of this marriage are said to have been the founders of the Hausa states. This fable most likely symbolizes the merger of Arabic/Berber migrations between 500 AD and 1400 AD. Most of the main towns and cities were walled and inter-city warfare was common. Around 1350-80 AD the Islamic faith was introduced into the region of Sokoto via what is now known as Mali, and Sokoto is still regarded as the spiritual and cultural centre of Northern Nigeria. Whilst this establishment of Islam encouraged commercial development in the region, new camel train routes were developed and Kano became the main commercial city.

Economically, the main crops were guinea corn, millet and rice supplemented by groundnuts, onions, beans, yams and sugar cane. The cash crop was cotton and indigo. Crafts observed by Barth and still practised in almost every village are pottery, spinning, weaving and dyeing. Smiths worked in gold, silver, copper and iron, the last being most important for the

manufacture of implements and weapons. In Bida, a small town situated 250 miles to the south of Sokoto, there is a group of glass workers. The sand is probably responsible for this craft's establishment, but its workers treasure the belief that their methods originated in Egypt. Tanners and leather workers existed in every main community, the principal areas being Kano and Sokoto. The quality of raw goatskin in Nigeria has always been best in Sokoto, slowly decreasing in standard as one moves eastward. The skins are dark red-haired in Sokoto, lighter red in Kano, white and black and white in Maidugari. Sokoto has always produced the best ironware as well as the finest leather, used in Europe since mediaeval times.

Genetic and Typological Categorization

Kraft and Kirk-Green (1994) as reported in Unubi and Yusuf (2017:416) declare that Hausa is classified by J. H. Greenberg as a member of the Chadic group of the Afroasiatic family of languages. It is, therefore, more closely related genetically to Arabic, Hebrew, Berber and other members of the Afroasiatic family than are most of the rest of the languages of sub-Saharan Africa. According to Jaggar (2011:1), Hausa, with perhaps as many as 40 million first-language speakers (within the Afroasiatic/Afrasian phylum only Arabic has more), is by far the largest of the 130 or more languages which constitute the Chadic family. Hausa covers most of the northern and western extent of the family, across northern Nigeria and into southern Niger. Chadic languages also extend into northern Cameroon and western and south-central parts of the Chad Republic, and hitherto unknown languages are still occasionally discovered. This area is one of the most linguistically complex in Africa, and is the location of languages belonging to three of the four great phyla as postulated by Greenberg (1963) – Afroasiatic (e.g., Hausa), Niger Kordofanian (e.g., Fulani), and Nilo-Saharan (e.g., Kanuri).

Jaggar (2011:1) also reports that Newman (1977, 1990), Newman and Ma (1966), and Jungraithmayr and Ibriszimow (1994) classify the Chadic family into four branches: *West Chadic-A* (including Hausa, Bole/Bolanci), *West Chadic-B* (Bade, Ngizim, etc.), *Biu-Mandara = Central Chadic* (languages in northeastern Nigeria, e.g., Tera, Margi, and northern Cameroon), *East Chadic* (western Chad Republic, e.g., Kera) with the closely related *Masa* group (western/central Chad Republic and northeastern Cameroon). It has also been claimed that Hausa is somehow descended from Semitic (or a Semitic language), an error which is probably attributable in part to the historical prominence of the peoples and cultures of the Near and Middle East (see Schuh 1997 for a critique of similar spurious claims regarding Hausa and Ancient Egyptian). Hausa, however,

like its Chadic cousins, does not derive from Semitic. Chadic and Semitic are coordinate families which both descend from the same ancestral source. Semitic, like Chadic, is merely one of six independent families within Afroasiatic, and Arabic and Hebrew are no more salient with respect to our scientific understanding of Afroasiatic than is a small Chadic language spoken by a few hundred people living on top of a hill in north-eastern Nigeria.

Regarding the evolution of the Chadic family itself, one generally accepted scenario is that after Proto-Afroasiatic split up, the ancestral core of Chadic subsequently spread westwards across the Sahara into the Lake Chad basin (5/6,000 years ago the "Green Sahara" had vegetation, lakes and wetlands, gradually transforming into an arid desert from about 3,000 BP). Historically Chadic languages were probably spoken from northwest Nigeria to their present extent in the Chad Republic, i.e., to the west and south of Lake Chad, and over time some were replaced by Hausa in the west, and by Kanembu and Chadian Arabic to the east. In addition, the linguistic geography of the family also looks invasive: Chadic languages are contiguous with Plateau and Adamawa languages, so communities of Chadic speakers presumably expanded south historically and displaced or interspersed with resident Niger-Kordofanian languages.

Below is a family tree of Afro-Asiatic languages clearly showing the position of Hausa:

Figure 2: The Genetic and Typological Classification of Hausa in the Afro-Asiatic Language Family (<https://www.google.com/afroasiatic+hausa+family>)

Sociolinguistic Sketch and Dialect Information

Throughout the areas where Hausa is spoken, it is remarkably uniform in pronunciation, vocabulary and structure. Indeed, the varieties of Hausa are at least mutually intelligible or comprehensible. Despite the basic uniformity of Hausa where it is spoken, one can identify a number of dialect areas. As it would be expected of a dynamic language with a large number of speakers, these dialects themselves show internal variation but each has a feature or cluster of features which are characteristic of that variety. Discussed below are some of the main dialects of Hausa:

(i) **Kano Hausa:** The Hausa spoken in Kano, the largest city in the contiguous Hausa-speaking area and the surrounding regions is usually referred to as *Standard Hausa*. This variety of Hausa is the one used in nearly all printed materials in Hausa, including the Hausa language newspapers in Nigeria. It is also the variety of Hausa most heard in broadcast media, including Nigerian radio and television as well as the international Hausa broadcasting such as the BBC, Deutsche Welle, the Voice of America (VOA), and others.

In pronunciation, a major feature characterising this dialect is seen in words such as *sauka* ‘descend’ or *zauna* ‘sit down’, where a *u* appears before another consonant rather than a *b* an *f* or an *m* in other dialects. Furthermore, in grammar, this dialect consistently distinguishes between masculine and feminine gender of all nouns just like the French language. For example, *suna ne* ‘it’s a name’ (where *ne* ‘it’s’ marks masculine) versus *giwa ce* ‘it’s an elephant’ (where *ce* ‘it’s’ marks feminine).

(ii) **Western Hausa:** The Hausa spoken roughly between Sokoto (Sakkwato) and Gusau in Nigeria, and north to Birnin Konni (Birnin Kwanni) and Tahoua (Tawa) in Niger comprises the Western Hausa. One might consider this variety ‘Classical Hausa’ for several reasons. First, it has proved quite conservative in terms of retaining features which can be identified as belonging to the more ancient stages of the language. Second, this was the variety of Hausa spoken by Shehu Usman Danfodio and his followers, who carries the jihad of Islamic reform in the early 19th century. Part of this reform movement involved the composition of Islamic poetry, which comprises the oldest extensive written documentation of Hausa and nearly all of which is in the Western dialect. Finally, the majority of Hausa praise-singers, who might be considered purveyors of classical Hausa music, are from the Western dialect area, and their music remains popular among all Hausa speakers.

In terms of pronunciation, speakers of Western Hausa still pronounce *b*, *f* and *m* when they come before other consonants. Thus, Western Hausa speakers say *sabka* ‘descend’ and *zamna* ‘sit down’, as compared with the Kano Hausa pronunciation of these words. In grammar, the Western Hausa also consistently distinguishes between masculine and feminine, as does the Kano dialect, but instead of the masculine *ne* ‘it’s’ and the feminine *ce* ‘it’s’, as in most of the rest of Hausa-speaking areas, the Western dialect uses *na* and *ta* respectively, e.g. *suna na* ‘it’s a name’ (masculine), *giwa ta* ‘it’s an elephant’ (feminine).

(iii) **Northern Hausa:**

The Hausa spoken along Nigeria-Niger border and into Niger comprises Northern Hausa. Some major cities in these areas are Katsina in Nigeria and Narad’i and Zinder in Niger. In terms of pronunciation, the Northern Hausa is similar to the Western one because its speakers still pronounce *b*, *f* and *m* when they come before other consonants. Thus, Northern Hausa speakers say *sabka* ‘descend’ and *zamna* ‘sit down’. As for grammar, in marking gender of nouns, the Northern Hausa has it in common with the Kano Hausa and so the words *ne* ‘it’s’ for masculine (*suna ne* ‘it’s a name’) and *ce* ‘it’s’ for feminine (*giwa ce* ‘it’s an elephant’). In a sense, the Northern Hausa is an intermediate dialect between the more conservative Western area and the more innovative Kano area.

(iv) **Southern Hausa:** This dialect of Hausa extends from the city of Zaria and its environs (the region called Zauzzau) to the Bauci area. Southern Hausa and Western Hausa are really sub-dialects of the larger Kano or Standard Hausa group. In terms of pronunciation, the Southern Hausa shares with the Kano Hausa the pronunciation of *u* in words such as *sauka* ‘descend’ or *zauna* ‘sit down’. Grammatically, the distinctive feature of Southern Hausa is the loss of gender distinction basically in all nouns except those referring to humans and some domestic animals. So, the feminine word *ce* ‘it’s’ is not used at all in Southern Hausa. For instance, the Southern Hausa speakers would say *yaro ne* ‘it’s a boy’ and *yarinya ne* ‘it’s a girl’. However, a gender distinction for humans does show up in pronoun agreement; e.g. *yaro ya zo* ‘the boy came’ (with *ya* showing masculine agreement) but *yarinya ta zo* ‘the girl came’ (with *ta* showing feminine agreement).

(v) **Eastern Hausa:** The Eastern Hausa (also known as Guddiri Hausa) has its area extending to cities of Had’aja, Katagum, Azare, Potiskum and other towns in the general vicinity. Like Southern Hausa, Eastern Hausa is actually a sub-dialect of the larger Kono variety. In pronunciation, Eastern and Western Hausas share the similar feature of *u* in words such as *sauka*

‘descend’ or *zauna* ‘sit down’. In grammar, Eastern Hausa has the same characteristics with respect to grammatical gender as Southern Hausa. In addition, the features distinctive to the Eastern Hausa involve somewhat technical aspects of grammar and morphology. One feature distinguishing this dialect from others is the placement of indirect objects after direct objects; e.g. *na tura yaro a Sarki* ‘I sent a boy to the king/chief’. In all other dialects, the indirect object comes first; e.g. Kano dialect – *na tura wa Sarki yaro*.

(vi) **Ghanian Hausa:** As the name implies, the *Ghanaian* Hausa is the variety spoken by the native speakers of Hausa in Ghana. Since Ghana is outside the contiguous native speaking Hausa area, it may not be possible to separate specific features of native Hausa in Ghana from non-native features typical of Ghanaian Hausa speakers who speak other languages. One feature typical of Ghanaian Hausa but not of any native varieties in Niger and Nigeria is the use of the sounds *che* and *j*, where Nigerian and Nigerien varieties would have *ky* and *gy* respectively; e.g. *cau* (chow) ‘beauty’ rather than *kyau* and *jara* ‘repair’ for *gyara*.

(vii) **Non-native Hausa:** Hausa is the main lingua franca throughout Niger and the northern two-thirds of Nigeria. It is also widely used as a lingua franca by Muslim population in other countries west of Nigeria; e.g. Benin, Togo and Ghana. Though there is no unified non-native Hausa dialect, certain features typically distinguish non-native from native speakers of Hausa. Phonologically, all native Hausa speakers would distinguish *karu* ‘be protected’ (with a plain *k*) from *karu* ‘be increased’ (with an ejective *k*) or *daidai* ‘correct’ (with plain *d*) from *daidai* ‘one at a time’ (with implosive *d*). Non-native speakers would pronounce both members of these pairs identically; e.g. using only the plain consonants. An adducible reason for this is that most West African languages lack a set of glottalised sounds (except few that are Hausa’s linguistic relatives in the Chadic family and Fula, which have implosive *b* and *d*).

As for grammatical gender distinction, all native speakers of Hausa would say *yaro ya tafi* ‘the boy left’ (with masculine singular agreement *ya*) but *yaringa ta tafi* ‘the girl left’ (with feminine singular agreement *ta*). Non-native speakers would typically use the masculine agreement *ya* for both of these. The reason for this is that most West African languages do not have grammatical gender distinction (e.g. Igala, Esan, Idoma, etc.) exceptions being some but not all Hausa’s linguistic relatives in the Chadic family and Tamazhaq, a Berber language to the north of Hausa (<http://aflang.linguistics.ucla.edu/Hausa/Language/dialects.html> with input from the researcher).

Genetic Relationship between Arabic and Hausa

Considering the family trees of both Arabic and Hausa languages presented in this study, it is unquestionably clear that there is a genetic and typological affinity between the two languages. Hausa is a member of the Chadic group of the Afro-asiatic family of languages, making it to be more closely related to Arabic, Hebrew, Berber and other members of the Afro-asiatic family than are most of the rest of the languages of sub-Saharan Africa. Furthermore, notice that both languages are of Semitic ancestral origin. The Semitic languages include Hausa, Arabic, Aramaic languages, Hebrew, extinct Phoenician and Akkadian; Berber languages; Ethiopian languages which includes Amharic, Gurage, Tigre and Tigrinya; and Cushitic languages which include Somali and Oromo. Due to the relationship between the two languages, Hausa was first written in an Arabic script known as ajami. Today this representation of the language is largely restricted to Muslim scholars, diviners (*malamai*) and their Koranic schools.

Conclusion

Clear significant linguistic information about a language or languages, such as the one provided here, can serve as a pivotal guide to the linguist. The reason is due to the fact that if the genetic, typological and philological origin of a language is sufficiently exposed, it is capable of guiding the linguist into insightful revelation of the phonological, morphological as well as syntactic behaviour of such languages. For example, from this research, we have been able to see clearly the genetic affinity between both the Hausa and Arabic languages. Bearing this in mind, the researcher was propelled to embark on this important but strenuous study.

Contribution to Knowledge

Aside the fact that this study will be an invaluable reference material for linguists, students of language, laymen and language enthusiasts both present and future, it can also serve as a guide or template for replicating similar studies in many Nigerian and African languages in particular and languages of the world in general. In addition, delving into and documenting, not only the genetic, typological and philological origins but also how the name of a language became extant, can be a potent weapon against language endangerment, extinction or death. Lastly, making this study available in the field of linguistics as an addition to the existing studies is a contribution to knowledge in linguistics.

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